

Some Modifications and Improvements to Idealization of j -Approximation Spaces

Rodyna A. Hosny^a, Mostafa K. El-Bably^{b,*}, Ashraf S. Nawar^c

^aMathematics Department, Faculty of Science, Zagazig University, Zagazig, Egypt.

^bMathematics Department, Faculty of Science, Tanta University, Tanta, Egypt.

^cDepartment of Mathematics and Computer Science, Faculty of Science, Menoufia University, Menoufia, Egypt.

Abstract

The core purpose of this paper is to point out some erroneous assertions given in the previous paper "Idealization of j -Approximation Spaces" [30]. In fact, we found some shortcomings and errors that need improvement and correction. Firstly, we prove that the relations given in the properties (6) and (7) in Proposition 4.1 are equal, not a subset or superset. Furthermore, we show that items (2), (3), (4), and (6) in Proposition 5.2 are incorrect in general. Additionally, counterexamples are given to confirm our claim. Finally, we illustrate that item (4) in Remarks 5.3 is also incorrect. Moreover, the correct form of the incorrect results in "Idealization of j -Approximation Spaces" is presented.

Keywords: j -Neighborhood space, Rough sets, Topology, Ideals.

1. Introduction

A rough set, performed by Pawlak [1], is an authoritative approximation of a conventional set expressed by a pair of sets that give the lower and the upper approximations of the premier set. The rough set theory is characterized by lower and upper approximations in terms of equivalence classes. Several extensions of this theory were presented, some of them were suggested for discussing rough sets via a topological method, such as ([2] – [28]). In [2], Abd El-Monsef et al. used the idea of a j -neighborhood space (j -NS) and utilized different general topologies deduced from binary relations to generalize the conventional rough set theory. The concept of "Ideal" represents an essential tool in topological spaces and is crucial in the study of topological problems and their other applications. Recently, Al-shami et al. [4] used this notion to define

*Corresponding author

Email addresses: hrodyna@yahoo.com (Rodyna A. Hosny), mkamel_bably@yahoo.com (Mostafa K. El-Bably), ashraf_nawar2020@yahoo.com (Ashraf S. Nawar)

some methods to generalize rough sets. Nawar et al. [28] also presented different kinds of generalized rough sets using the notion of a $\theta\beta$ -ideal. By different methods based on ideals, which were initiated by Kuratowski [29], M. Hosny [30] generated different topologies, that were used to generalize the fundamental concepts of rough set theory. However, we note some errors in [30]. In the first kind of erroneous results found in Proposition 4.1 [30], we improve the properties (6, 7). Namely, we demonstrate that the relations are given in the properties (6) and (7) are equality relations, not a subset or superset. Secondly, the items (2), (3), (4), and (6) in Proposition 5.2 are not true. To this end, we presented some counterexamples to approve our claim. Lastly, we introduce an example to illustrate that item (4) in Remarks 5.3 is also false. Besides, the correct form of the incorrect results in [30] is presented.

2. Preliminaries

Definition 2.1. [31] A non-empty collection $\mathcal{I}$ of subsets of a set U is called an ideal on U , if it satisfies the following

1. $A \in \mathcal{I}$ and $B \in \mathcal{I} \implies A \cup B \in \mathcal{I}$, and
2. $A \in \mathcal{I}$ and $B \subseteq A \implies B \in \mathcal{I}$.

Definition 2.2. [2] Let R be a binary relation on a nonempty finite set (universe) U . The j -neighborhoods of $x \in U$, $N_j(x)$, $\forall j \in \{r, l, i, u, \langle r \rangle, \langle l \rangle, \langle i \rangle, \langle u \rangle\}$ with respect to R , are defined as:

1. r -neighborhood: $N_r(x) = \{y \in U : xRy\}$.
2. l -neighborhood: $N_l(x) = \{y \in U : yRx\}$.
3. i -neighborhood: $N_i(x) = N_r(x) \cap N_l(x)$.
4. u -neighborhood: $N_u(x) = N_r(x) \cup N_l(x)$.
5. $\langle r \rangle$ -neighborhood: $N_{\langle r \rangle}(x) = \cap \{N_r(y) : x \in N_r(y)\}$.
6. $\langle l \rangle$ -neighborhood: $N_{\langle l \rangle}(x) = \cap \{N_l(y) : x \in N_l(y)\}$.
7. $\langle i \rangle$ -neighborhood: $N_{\langle i \rangle}(x) = N_{\langle r \rangle}(x) \cap N_{\langle l \rangle}(x)$.
8. $\langle u \rangle$ -neighborhood: $N_{\langle u \rangle}(x) = N_{\langle r \rangle}(x) \cup N_{\langle l \rangle}(x)$.

Definition 2.3. [2] Let R be a binary relation on a universe U and $\xi_j: U \rightarrow P(U)$ be a mapping which assigns for each x in U its j -neighborhood in $P(U)$. Then (U, R, ξ_j) is called a j -neighborhood space (briefly, j -NS).

Theorem 2.4. [30] Let (U, R, ξ_j) be a j -NS. If $A \subseteq U$, then $\forall j \in \{r, l, i, u, \langle r \rangle, \langle l \rangle, \langle i \rangle, \langle u \rangle\}$, the collection $\tau_j = \{A \subseteq U : \forall x \in A, N_j(x) \subseteq A\}$ is a topology on U .

Theorem 2.5. [30] Let (U, R, ξ_j) be a j -NS and $\mathcal{I}$ be an ideal on U . If $A \subseteq U$, then $\forall j \in \{r, l, i, u, \langle r \rangle, \langle l \rangle, \langle i \rangle, \langle u \rangle\}$, the collection $\tau_j^{\mathcal{I}} = \{A \subseteq U : \forall x \in A, N_j(x) \cap A^c \in \mathcal{I}\}$ is a topology on U .

Definition 2.6. [30] Let (U, R, ξ_j) be a j -NS and $\mathcal{I}$ be an ideal on U . A set $A \subseteq U$ is called $\mathcal{I}_j$ -open set if $A \in \tau_j^{\mathcal{I}}$, and the complement of $\mathcal{I}_j$ -open set is called $\mathcal{I}_j$ -closed set. The family $\Gamma_j^{\mathcal{I}}$ of all $\mathcal{I}_j$ -closed sets of a j -neighborhood space is defined by $\Gamma_j^{\mathcal{I}} = \{F \subseteq U : F^c \in \tau_j^{\mathcal{I}}\}$.

Definition 2.7. [30] Let (U, R, ξ_j) be a j -NS and $\mathcal{I}$ be an ideal on U , $\forall j \in \{r, l, i, u, \langle r \rangle, \langle l \rangle, \langle i \rangle, \langle u \rangle\}$. If $A \subseteq U$, then the $\mathcal{I}_j$ -lower and $\mathcal{I}_j$ -upper approximations of A are defined respectively as:

1. $\underline{R}_j^{\mathcal{I}}(A) = \cup \{G \in \tau_j^{\mathcal{I}} : G \subseteq A\} = \text{int}_j^{\mathcal{I}}(A)$, and
2. $\overline{R}_j^{\mathcal{I}}(A) = \cap \{H \in \Gamma_j^{\mathcal{I}} : A \subseteq H\} = \text{cl}_j^{\mathcal{I}}(A)$.

Definition 2.8. [30] Let (U, R, ξ_j) be a j -NS ($j \in \{r, l, i, u, \langle r \rangle, \langle l \rangle, \langle i \rangle, \langle u \rangle\}$) and $\mathcal{I}$ be an ideal on U . If $A \subseteq U$, then $\underline{\underline{R}}_j^{\mathcal{I}}(A)$, and $\overline{\overline{R}}_j^{\mathcal{I}}(A)$ are defined respectively as:

1. $\underline{\underline{R}}_j^{\mathcal{I}}(A) = \cup \{G \in \tau_j^{\mathcal{I}} : G \cap A^c \in \mathcal{I}\}$, and
2. $\overline{\overline{R}}_j^{\mathcal{I}}(A) = \cap \{H \in \Gamma_j^{\mathcal{I}} : A \cap H^c \in \mathcal{I}\}$.

Table 1: Comparison between $\mathcal{I}_j$ -lower approximation, $j \in \{r, l, i, u, < r \rangle, < l \rangle, < i \rangle, < u \rangle\}$

$A \subseteq U$	$\underline{R}_r^{\mathcal{I}}(A)$	$\underline{R}_l^{\mathcal{I}}(A)$	$\underline{R}_i^{\mathcal{I}}(A)$	$\underline{R}_u^{\mathcal{I}}(A)$	$\underline{R}_{\langle r \rangle}^{\mathcal{I}}(A)$	$\underline{R}_{\langle l \rangle}^{\mathcal{I}}(A)$	$\underline{R}_{\langle i \rangle}^{\mathcal{I}}(A)$	$\underline{R}_{\langle u \rangle}^{\mathcal{I}}(A)$
$\{a\}$	$\{a\}$	$\{a\}$	$\{a\}$	$\{a\}$	$\{a\}$	$\{a\}$	$\{a\}$	$\{a\}$
$\{b\}$	$\{b\}$	$\emptyset$	$\{b\}$	$\emptyset$	$\emptyset$	$\emptyset$	$\emptyset$	$\emptyset$
$\{c\}$	$\emptyset$	$\emptyset$	$\{c\}$	$\emptyset$	$\{c\}$	$\{c\}$	$\{c\}$	$\{c\}$
$\{d\}$	$\{d\}$	$\{d\}$	$\{d\}$	$\{d\}$	$\{d\}$	$\{d\}$	$\{d\}$	$\{d\}$
$\{a, b\}$	$\{a, b\}$	$\{a, b\}$	$\{a, b\}$	$\{a, b\}$	$\{a, b\}$	$\{a, b\}$	$\{a, b\}$	$\{a, b\}$
$\{a, c\}$	$\{a\}$	$\{a, c\}$	$\{a, c\}$	$\{a\}$	$\{a, c\}$	$\{a, c\}$	$\{a, c\}$	$\{a, c\}$
$\{a, d\}$	$\{a, d\}$	$\{a, d\}$	$\{a, d\}$	$\{a, d\}$	$\{a, d\}$	$\{a, d\}$	$\{a, d\}$	$\{a, d\}$
$\{b, c\}$	$\{b\}$	$\emptyset$	$\{b, c\}$	$\emptyset$	$\{c\}$	$\{c\}$	$\{c\}$	$\{c\}$
$\{b, d\}$	$\{b, d\}$	$\{d\}$	$\{b, d\}$	$\{d\}$	$\{d\}$	$\{d\}$	$\{d\}$	$\{d\}$
$\{c, d\}$	$\{c, d\}$	$\{d\}$	$\{c, d\}$	$\{d\}$	$\{c, d\}$	$\{c, d\}$	$\{c, d\}$	$\{c, d\}$
$\{a, b, c\}$	$\{a, b\}$	$\{a, b, c\}$	$\{a, b, c\}$	$\{a, b\}$	$\{a, b, c\}$	$\{a, b, c\}$	$\{a, b, c\}$	$\{a, b, c\}$
$\{a, b, d\}$	$\{a, b, d\}$	$\{a, b, d\}$	$\{a, b, d\}$	$\{a, b, d\}$	$\{a, b, d\}$	$\{a, b, d\}$	$\{a, b, d\}$	$\{a, b, d\}$
$\{a, c, d\}$	$\{a, c, d\}$	$\{a, c, d\}$	$\{a, c, d\}$	$\{a, c, d\}$	$\{a, c, d\}$	$\{a, c, d\}$	$\{a, c, d\}$	$\{a, c, d\}$
$\{b, c, d\}$	$\{b, c, d\}$	$\{d\}$	$\{b, c, d\}$	$\{d\}$	$\{c, d\}$	$\{c, d\}$	$\{c, d\}$	$\{c, d\}$
U	U	U	U	U	U	U	U	U

3. Main Results and counter examples

In this part, we indicate where the faults happen in [30] and then accord counter examples to illustrate our claim. Furthermore, the correct form of these errors is given.

Firstly, to clarify some of the errors mentioned in [30], we will deal with Example 3.1, which is the same as Example 3.1 of [30] after correcting the errors that happened.

Example 3.1. Let R be a binary relation on $U = \{a, b, c, d\}$, defined as

$$R = \{(a, a), (a, b), (a, c), (b, c), (c, d)\}.$$

$$\tau_r = \{\emptyset, U, \{d\}, \{c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}\}.$$

$$\tau_l = \{\emptyset, U, \{a\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, b, c\}\}.$$

$$\tau_i = P(U).$$

$$\tau_u = \{\emptyset, U\}.$$

$$\tau_{\langle r \rangle} = \{\emptyset, U, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, b, c\}\}.$$

$$\tau_{\langle l \rangle} = \{\emptyset, U, \{a\}, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, \{a, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, c, d\}\}.$$

$$\tau_{\langle i \rangle} = \{\emptyset, U, \{a\}, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, \{a, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, c, d\}\}.$$

$$\tau_{\langle u \rangle} = \{\emptyset, U, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, b, c\}\}.$$

Suppose that $\mathcal{I} = \{\emptyset, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{b, c\}\}$ is an ideal on U .

$$\tau_r^{\mathcal{I}} = \{\emptyset, U, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{d\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, d\}, \{b, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}\}.$$

$$\tau_l^{\mathcal{I}} = \{\emptyset, U, \{a\}, \{d\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, \{a, d\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{a, b, c\}\}.$$

$$\tau_i^{\mathcal{I}} = P(U).$$

$$\tau_u^{\mathcal{I}} = \{\emptyset, U, \{a\}, \{d\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, d\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, c, d\}\}.$$

$$\tau_{\langle r \rangle}^{\mathcal{I}} = \{\emptyset, U, \{a\}, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, \{a, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{a, b, c\}\}.$$

$$\tau_{\langle l \rangle}^{\mathcal{I}} = \{\emptyset, U, \{a\}, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, \{a, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{a, b, c\}\}.$$

$$\tau_{\langle i \rangle}^{\mathcal{I}} = \{\emptyset, U, \{a\}, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, \{a, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{a, b, c\}\}.$$

$$\tau_{\langle u \rangle}^{\mathcal{I}} = \{\emptyset, U, \{a\}, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, \{a, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{a, b, c\}\}.$$

Therefore, Tables 1 and 2 present the $\mathcal{I}_j$ -lower and $\mathcal{I}_j$ -upper approximations of all subsets of U .

Table 2: Comparison between $\mathcal{I}_j$ -upper approximation, $j \in \{r, l, i, u, < r >, < l >, < i >, < u >\}$

$A \subseteq U$	$\overline{R}_r^{\mathcal{I}}(A)$	$\overline{R}_l^{\mathcal{I}}(A)$	$\overline{R}_i^{\mathcal{I}}(A)$	$\overline{R}_u^{\mathcal{I}}(A)$	$\overline{R}_{<r>}^{\mathcal{I}}(A)$	$\overline{R}_{<l>}^{\mathcal{I}}(A)$	$\overline{R}_{<i>}^{\mathcal{I}}(A)$	$\overline{R}_{<u>}^{\mathcal{I}}(A)$
$\{a\}$	$\{a\}$	$\{a, b, c\}$	$\{a\}$	$\{a, b, c\}$	$\{a, b\}$	$\{a, b\}$	$\{a, b\}$	$\{a, b\}$
$\{b\}$	$\{b\}$	$\{b\}$	$\{b\}$	$\{b\}$	$\{b\}$	$\{b\}$	$\{b\}$	$\{b\}$
$\{c\}$	$\{c\}$	$\{c\}$	$\{c\}$	$\{c\}$	$\{c\}$	$\{c\}$	$\{c\}$	$\{c\}$
$\{d\}$	$\{c, d\}$	$\{d\}$	$\{d\}$	$\{c, d\}$	$\{d\}$	$\{d\}$	$\{d\}$	$\{d\}$
$\{a, b\}$	$\{a, b\}$	$\{a, b, c\}$	$\{a, b\}$	$\{a, b, c\}$	$\{a, b\}$	$\{a, b\}$	$\{a, b\}$	$\{a, b\}$
$\{a, c\}$	$\{a, c\}$	$\{a, b, c\}$	$\{a, c\}$	$\{a, b, c\}$	$\{a, b, c\}$	$\{a, b, c\}$	$\{a, b, c\}$	$\{a, b, c\}$
$\{a, d\}$	$\{a, c, d\}$	U	$\{a, d\}$	U	$\{a, b, d\}$	$\{a, b, d\}$	$\{a, b, d\}$	$\{a, b, d\}$
$\{b, c\}$	$\{b, c\}$	$\{b, c\}$	$\{b, c\}$	$\{b, c\}$	$\{b, c\}$	$\{b, c\}$	$\{b, c\}$	$\{b, c\}$
$\{b, d\}$	$\{b, c, d\}$	$\{b, d\}$	$\{b, d\}$	$\{b, c, d\}$	$\{b, d\}$	$\{b, d\}$	$\{b, d\}$	$\{b, d\}$
$\{c, d\}$	$\{c, d\}$	$\{c, d\}$	$\{c, d\}$	$\{c, d\}$	$\{c, d\}$	$\{c, d\}$	$\{c, d\}$	$\{c, d\}$
$\{a, b, c\}$	$\{a, b, c\}$	$\{a, b, c\}$	$\{a, b, c\}$	$\{a, b, c\}$	$\{a, b, c\}$	$\{a, b, c\}$	$\{a, b, c\}$	$\{a, b, c\}$
$\{a, b, d\}$	U	U	$\{a, b, d\}$	U	$\{a, b, d\}$	$\{a, b, d\}$	$\{a, b, d\}$	$\{a, b, d\}$
$\{a, c, d\}$	$\{a, c, d\}$	U	$\{a, c, d\}$	U	U	U	U	U
$\{b, c, d\}$	$\{b, c, d\}$	$\{b, c, d\}$	$\{b, c, d\}$	$\{b, c, d\}$	$\{b, c, d\}$	$\{b, c, d\}$	$\{b, c, d\}$	$\{b, c, d\}$
U	U	U	U	U	U	U	U	U

In [[30], Proposition 4.1, p. 292], the author introduced the properties (6, 7) of Proposition 4.1 as follows:

For any subsets A, B of a j -NS (U, R, ξ_j) ($j \in \{r, l, i, u, < r >, < l >, < i >, < u >\}$) with an ideal $\mathcal{I}$ on U ,

- $\underline{R}_j^{\mathcal{I}}(A \cap B) \subseteq \underline{R}_j^{\mathcal{I}}(A) \cap \underline{R}_j^{\mathcal{I}}(B)$.
- $\overline{R}_j^{\mathcal{I}}(A \cup B) \supseteq \overline{R}_j^{\mathcal{I}}(A) \cup \overline{R}_j^{\mathcal{I}}(B)$.

In the next result, we improve the properties (6, 7) of Proposition 4.1 [30]. In fact, we illustrate that for all $j \in \{r, l, i, u, < r >, < l >, < i >, < u >\}$, these properties are equality, not subset or superset. Thus, the next proposition represents the correct form of [Proposition 4.1, p. 292] in [30].

Proposition 3.2. Let (U, R, ξ_j) be a j -NS ($j \in \{r, l, i, u, < r >, < l >, < i >, < u >\}$) and $\mathcal{I}$ be an ideal on U . If $A, B \subseteq U$, then the following statements hold:

- $\underline{R}_j^{\mathcal{I}}(A \cap B) = \underline{R}_j^{\mathcal{I}}(A) \cap \underline{R}_j^{\mathcal{I}}(B)$.
- $\overline{R}_j^{\mathcal{I}}(A \cup B) = \overline{R}_j^{\mathcal{I}}(A) \cup \overline{R}_j^{\mathcal{I}}(B)$.

Proof. 1. Obviously $\underline{R}_j^{\mathcal{I}}(A \cap B) \subseteq \underline{R}_j^{\mathcal{I}}(A) \cap \underline{R}_j^{\mathcal{I}}(B)$. The other side, $x \in \underline{R}_j^{\mathcal{I}}(A) \cap \underline{R}_j^{\mathcal{I}}(B)$, then there exist $G_1, G_2 \in \tau_j^{\mathcal{I}}$ such that $G_1 \subseteq A$ and $G_2 \subseteq B$. Therefore, $G = G_1 \cap G_2 \in \tau_j^{\mathcal{I}}$ where $G \subseteq A \cap B$ and so $x \in \underline{R}_j^{\mathcal{I}}(A \cap B)$. Consequently, $\underline{R}_j^{\mathcal{I}}(A \cap B) = \underline{R}_j^{\mathcal{I}}(A) \cap \underline{R}_j^{\mathcal{I}}(B)$.

2. In a similar way to (1) and by using the property $\overline{R}_j^{\mathcal{I}}(A) = (\underline{R}_j^{\mathcal{I}}(A^c))^c$ in [30], the proof is obvious.

Note that: Example 3.1 illustrated the above proposition.

In [[30], Proposition 5.2, p. 297], the author introduced the properties (2), (3), (4) and (6) of Proposition 5.2:

For any subsets A, B of a j -NS (U, R, ξ_j) ($j \in \{r, l, i, u, < r >, < l >, < i >, < u >\}$) with ideals $\mathcal{I}, \mathcal{J}$ on U

- If $A \subseteq B$, then $\overline{\overline{R}}_j^{\mathcal{I}}(B) \subseteq \overline{\overline{R}}_j^{\mathcal{I}}(A)$.

2. $\overline{\overline{\mathcal{I}}}_j(A \cap B) \supseteq \overline{\overline{\mathcal{I}}}_j(A) \cap \overline{\overline{\mathcal{I}}}_j(B)$.
3. $\overline{\overline{\mathcal{I}}}_j(A \cup B) \subseteq \overline{\overline{\mathcal{I}}}_j(A) \cup \overline{\overline{\mathcal{I}}}_j(B)$.
4. If $\mathcal{I} \subseteq \mathcal{J}$, then $\overline{\overline{\mathcal{I}}}_j(A) \subseteq \overline{\overline{\mathcal{J}}}_j(A)$.

Remark 3.3. According to Example 3.1 (if $j = u$) we obtain that the properties (1), and (2) are incorrect as follows:

1. Let $A = \{b\}$, and $B = \{a, b\}$. Then $\overline{\overline{\mathcal{I}}}_u(A) = \emptyset$, and $\overline{\overline{\mathcal{I}}}_u(B) = \{a, b, c\}$. Clearly, $\overline{\overline{\mathcal{I}}}_u(B) \not\subseteq \overline{\overline{\mathcal{I}}}_u(A)$.
2. Let $A = \{d\}$, and $B = \{a, b\}$. Then $A \cap B = \emptyset$ and hence $\overline{\overline{\mathcal{I}}}_u(A) = \{c, d\}$, $\overline{\overline{\mathcal{I}}}_u(B) = \{a, b, c\}$, and $\overline{\overline{\mathcal{I}}}_u(A) \cap \overline{\overline{\mathcal{I}}}_u(B) = \{c\}$. Clearly, $\overline{\overline{\mathcal{I}}}_u(A) \cap \overline{\overline{\mathcal{I}}}_u(B) \not\subseteq \overline{\overline{\mathcal{I}}}_u(A \cap B)$.

Remark 3.4. The following example illustrates that the property (4) [the property (6) of Proposition 5.2 in [30]] is not true as follows:

Example 3.5. On $U = \{a, b, c, d\}$, R is a binary relation on U defined as $R = \{(a, a), (a, b), (a, c), (b, c), (c, d)\}$. Suppose that $\mathcal{I} = \{\emptyset, \{b\}\}$ and $\mathcal{J} = \{\emptyset, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{b, c\}\}$ are ideals on U . Then,
 $\tau_r^{\mathcal{I}} = \{\emptyset, U, \{d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}\}$.
 $\tau_r^{\mathcal{J}} = \{\emptyset, U, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{d\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, d\}, \{b, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}\}$.

Now, let $A = \{c\}$. Then $\overline{\overline{\mathcal{I}}}_r(A) = \{a, b, c\}$, and $\overline{\overline{\mathcal{J}}}_r(A) = \emptyset$ which means that $\overline{\overline{\mathcal{I}}}_r(A) \not\subseteq \overline{\overline{\mathcal{J}}}_r(A)$.

Remark 3.6. The following proposition illustrates that the property (3) [the property (4) of Proposition 5.2 in [30]] represents an equality relation, not a subset or superset. Accordingly, it is the correction form of [Proposition 5.2, p. 297] in [30].

Proposition 3.7. Let (U, R, ξ_j) be a j -NS ($j \in \{r, l, i, u, < r >, < l >, < i >, < u >\}$) and $\mathcal{I}, \mathcal{J}$ be two ideals on U . If $A, B \subseteq U$, then the following properties hold:

1. If $A \subseteq B$, then $\overline{\overline{\mathcal{I}}}_j(A) \subseteq \overline{\overline{\mathcal{I}}}_j(B)$.
2. $\overline{\overline{\mathcal{I}}}_j(A \cap B) \subseteq \overline{\overline{\mathcal{I}}}_j(A) \cap \overline{\overline{\mathcal{I}}}_j(B)$.
3. $\overline{\overline{\mathcal{I}}}_j(A \cup B) = \overline{\overline{\mathcal{I}}}_j(A) \cup \overline{\overline{\mathcal{I}}}_j(B)$.
4. If $\mathcal{I} \subseteq \mathcal{J}$, then $\overline{\overline{\mathcal{I}}}_j(A) \subseteq \overline{\overline{\mathcal{J}}}_j(A)$.

Proof. 1. Suppose $x \notin \overline{\overline{\mathcal{I}}}_j(B)$, then there exists $H \in \Gamma_j^{\mathcal{I}}$ s.t. $x \notin H$ and $B \cap H^c \in \mathcal{I}$. Since $A \subseteq B$, then $A \cap H^c \in \mathcal{I}$. This implies that $x \notin \overline{\overline{\mathcal{I}}}_j(A)$ and so $\overline{\overline{\mathcal{I}}}_j(A) \subseteq \overline{\overline{\mathcal{I}}}_j(B)$.

2. In view of (1), $\overline{\overline{\mathcal{I}}}_j(A \cap B) \subseteq \overline{\overline{\mathcal{I}}}_j(A) \cap \overline{\overline{\mathcal{I}}}_j(B)$.

3. In view of (1), $\overline{\overline{\mathcal{I}}}_j(A) \cup \overline{\overline{\mathcal{I}}}_j(B) \subseteq \overline{\overline{\mathcal{I}}}_j(A \cup B)$. The other side, $x \notin \overline{\overline{\mathcal{I}}}_j(A) \cup \overline{\overline{\mathcal{I}}}_j(B)$, then there exist $H_1, H_2 \in \Gamma_j^{\mathcal{I}}$ s.t. $x \notin H_1 \cup H_2$, $A \cap H_1^c \in \mathcal{I}$ and $B \cap H_2^c \in \mathcal{I}$. Hence $A \cap (H_1^c \cap H_2^c) \in \mathcal{I}$ and $B \cap (H_1^c \cap H_2^c) \in \mathcal{I}$. Take $H = H_1 \cup H_2$. From ideals properties, then $[A \cap H^c] \cup [B \cap H^c] \in \mathcal{I}$ and so $(A \cup B) \cap H^c \in \mathcal{I}$. Consequently, $\overline{\overline{\mathcal{I}}}_j(A \cup B) \subseteq \overline{\overline{\mathcal{I}}}_j(A) \cup \overline{\overline{\mathcal{I}}}_j(B)$ and so $\overline{\overline{\mathcal{I}}}_j(A \cup B) = \overline{\overline{\mathcal{I}}}_j(A) \cup \overline{\overline{\mathcal{I}}}_j(B)$.

4. Let $x \notin \overline{\overline{\mathcal{I}}}_j(A)$, then there exist $H \in \Gamma_j^{\mathcal{I}}$ such that $x \notin H$ and $A \cap H^c \in \mathcal{I}$. Since $\mathcal{I} \subseteq \mathcal{J}$, hence $x \notin \overline{\overline{\mathcal{J}}}_j(A)$ and so $\overline{\overline{\mathcal{I}}}_j(A) \subseteq \overline{\overline{\mathcal{J}}}_j(A)$.

In [[30], Remark 5.3, p. 297], the author introduced the property (4) as follows:

For any subsets A of a j -NS (U, R, ξ_j) ($j \in \{r, l, i, u, < r >, < l >, < i >, < u >\}$) with ideal $\mathcal{I}$ on U $\overline{\overline{R}}_j^{\mathcal{I}}(A) \neq (\underline{R}_j^{\mathcal{I}}(A^c))^c$ and $\underline{R}_j^{\mathcal{I}}(A) \neq (\overline{\overline{R}}_j^{\mathcal{I}}(A^c))^c$.

The following proposition demonstrates this property is not true. Besides, it gives the correct form of [Remark 5.3, p. 297] in [30]. Moreover, Example 3.1 illustrates this proposition (in case of $j = r$).

Proposition 3.8. Let (U, R, ξ_j) be a j -NS ($j \in \{r, l, i, u, < r >, < l >, < i >, < u >\}$) and $\mathcal{I}$ be an ideal on U . If $A \subseteq U$, then $\overline{\overline{R}}_j^{\mathcal{I}}(A) = (\underline{R}_j^{\mathcal{I}}(A^c))^c$ and $\underline{R}_j^{\mathcal{I}}(A) = (\overline{\overline{R}}_j^{\mathcal{I}}(A^c))^c$.

Proof. $[\underline{R}_j^{\mathcal{I}}(A^c)]^c = [\cup\{G \in \tau_j^{\mathcal{I}} : G \cap A \in \mathcal{I}\}]^c = \cap\{G^c \in \Gamma_j^{\mathcal{I}} : A \cap G \in \mathcal{I}\} = \overline{\overline{R}}_j^{\mathcal{I}}(A)$. Similarly, we can prove $\underline{R}_j^{\mathcal{I}}(A) = (\overline{\overline{R}}_j^{\mathcal{I}}(A^c))^c$.

4. Conclusion

In this article, we have corrected some errors in the paper "Idealization of j -Approximation Spaces [30]". Firstly, we have presented a correction for Example 3.1 in [30] and thus, we have used it to illustrate some results in the present paper. Several counterexamples were presented to confirm the erroneous in [30]. In the first error found in Proposition 4.1, we have demonstrated that the relations given in the properties (6) and (7) are equality relations, not a subset or superset. Secondly, we have illustrated that the items (2), (3), (4), and (6) in Proposition 5.2 are not true. Lastly, we have introduced an example to illustrate that item (4) in Remark 5.3 is also false. Besides, we have introduced and proved the corrected form of these results.

Author Contributions

All authors contributed equally to this work. They all read and approved the last version of the manuscript.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

- [1] Z. Pawlak, *Rough sets*, Int. J. of Information and Computer Sciences **11** (1982), no. 5, 341–356.
- [2] M. E. Abd El-Monsef, O. A. Embaby and M. K. El-Bably, *Comparison between rough set approximations based on different topologies*, Int. J. of Granular Computing, Rough Set and Intelligent Systems **3** (2014), no. 4, 292–305.
- [3] M. Abdelaziz, H. M. Abu-Donia, R. A. Hosny, S. L. Hazae and R. A. Ibrahim, *Improved evolutionary-based feature selection technique using extension of knowledge based on the rough approximations*, Information Sciences **594** (2022), 76–94.
- [4] T. M. Al-shami, H. Işık, A. S Nawar and R. A. Hosny, *Some topological approaches for generalized rough sets via ideals*, Mathematical Problems in Engineering **2021** (2021), Article ID 5642982.
- [5] T. M. Al-shami, I. Alshammari and M. E. El-Shafei, *A comparison of two types of rough approximations based on N_j -neighborhoods*, Journal of Intelligent & Fuzzy Systems **41** (2021), no. 1, 1393–1406.
- [6] T. M. Al-shami, W. Q. Fu and E. A. Abo-Tabl, *New rough approximations based on E -neighborhoods*, Complexity **2021** (2021), Article ID 6666853, 6 pages.
- [7] E. A. Abo-Tabl and M. K. El-Bably, *Rough topological structure based on reflexivity with some applications*, AIMS Mathematics **7** (2022), no. 6, 9911–9925.
- [8] A. A. Allam, M. Y. Bakeir and E. A. Abo-Tabl, *New approach for basic rough set concepts*, International workshop on rough sets, fuzzy sets, data mining, and granular computing. Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence, 3641, Springer, Regina, 64–73, 2005.
- [9] E. A. Abo-Tabl, *Rough sets and topological spaces based on similarity*, International Journal of Machine Learning and Cybernetics **4** (2013), 451–458.

- [10] E. A. Abo-Tabl, *Topological approximations of multisets*, Journal of the Egyptian Mathematical Society **21** (2013), no. 2, 123–132.
- [11] E. A. Abo-Tabl, *On topological properties of generalized rough multisets*, Annals of Fuzzy Mathematics and Informatics **19** (2020), no. 1, 95–107.
- [12] M. A. El-Gayar and A. A. El-Atik, *Topological Models of Rough Sets and Decision Making of COVID-19*, Complexity; Hoboken **2022** (2022).
- [13] R. A. Hosny, M. Abdelaziz and R. A. Ibrahim, *Enhanced Feature Selection Based on Integration Containment Neighborhoods Rough Set Approximations and Binary Honey Badger Optimization*, Computational Intelligence and Neuroscience **2022** (2022), Article ID 3991870, 17 pages.
- [14] R. Abu-Gdairi, M. A. El-Gayar, T. M. Al-shami, A. S. Nawar and M. K. El-Bably, *Some topological approaches for generalized rough sets and their decision-making applications*, Symmetry **14** (2022), no. 1, 95.
- [15] R. Abu-Gdairi, M. A. El-Gayar, M. K. El-Bably and Kamel K. Fleifel, *Two different views for generalized rough sets with applications*, Mathematics **9** (2022), no. 18, 2275.
- [16] H. Lu, A. M. Khalil, W. Alharbi and M. A. El-Gayar, *A new type of generalized picture fuzzy soft set and its application in decision making*, Journal of Intelligent and Fuzzy Systems **40** (2021), no. 6, 12459–12475.
- [17] M. K. El-Bably and M. El-Sayed, *Three methods to generalize Pawlak approximations via simply open concepts with economic applications*, Soft Computing (2022).
- [18] M. K. El-Bably and T. M Al-Shami, *Different kinds of generalized rough sets based on neighborhoods with a medical application*, International Journal of Biomathematics **14** (2021), no. 8, 2150086.
- [19] M. K. El-Bably and E. A. Abo-Tabl, *A topological reduction for predicting of a lung cancer disease based on generalized rough sets*, Journal of Intelligent & Fuzzy Systems **41** (2021), no. 2, 3045–3060.
- [20] M. K. El-Bably, M. I. Ali and E. A. Abo-Tabl, *New topological approaches to generalized soft rough approximations with medical applications*, Journal of Mathematics **2021** (2021), Article ID 2559495, 16 pages.
- [21] M. K. El-Bably and A. El Atik, *Soft β -rough sets and their application to determine COVID-19*, Turkish Journal of Mathematics **45** (2021), no. 3, 1133–1148.
- [22] M. I. Ali, M. K. El-Bably and E. A. Abo-Tabl, *Topological approach to generalized soft rough sets via near concepts*, Soft Computing **26** (2022), no. 5, 499–509.
- [23] M. Atef, A. El Atik and A. S. Nawar, *Fuzzy topological structures via fuzzy graphs and their applications*, Soft Computing **25** (2021), no. 8, 6013–6027.
- [24] K. Kin, J. Yang and Z. Pei, *Generalized rough sets based on reflexive and transitive relations*, Information Sciences **178** (2008), no. 21, 4138–4141.
- [25] M. Kondo, *On structure of generalized rough sets*, Information Sciences, **176** (2006), no. 5, 589–600.
- [26] M. E. Abd El-Monsef, M. A. El-Gayar and R. M. Aqeel, *A comparison of three types of rough fuzzy sets based on two universal sets*. Int. J. Mach. Learn. and Cyber. **8** (2017), 343–353.
- [27] Y. Y. Yao, *Two views of the theory of rough sets in finite universes*, International Journal of Approximation Reasoning **15** (1996), 291–317.
- [28] A. S. Nawar, M. A. El-Gayar, M. K. El-Bably and R. A. Hosny, *$\theta\beta$ -ideal approximation spaces and their applications*, AIMS Mathematics **7** (2022), no. 2, 2479–2497.
- [29] K. Kuratowski, *Topology Vol. I*, Academic Press, New York, 1966.
- [30] M. Hosny, *Idealization of j -Approximation Spaces*, Filomat **34** (2020), no. 2, 287–301.
- [31] D. Jankovic and T. R. Hamlet, *New topologies from old via ideals*, Amer. Math. Monthly **97** (1990), 295–310.